

Circular valorization of *Hypericum perforatum* biomass into CuO-lignin and CuO-cellulose bionanocomposites for mitigating copper nanotoxicity in plants

Megha Saxena^a, Lakshmiopathy Muthukrishnan^a, Matam Pradeep^a,
Rajendran K. Selvakesavan^a, Gregory Franklin^{a,*}, Dibyendu Mondal^{a,b,*}

^a Institute' of Plant Genetics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Strzeszyńska 34, 60-479 Poznan, Poland

^b Centre for Nano and Material Sciences, Jain (Deemed-to-be University), Jain Global Campus, Kanakapura, Bangalore, Karnataka 562112, India

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ABSTRACT

We present a circular biomass valorisation strategy for the synthesis of CuO-based nanocomposites (NCs) using *Hypericum perforatum* L. In this approach, *H. perforatum* serves a dual purpose: its phytochemicals are used to synthesize CuO nanoparticles (NPs), while the remaining biomass is used to extract lignin and cellulose. The extracted lignin and cellulose were then processed into lignin nanoparticles (LNPs) and cellulose nanofibers (CNFs). These were subsequently functionalized with CuO NPs to fabricate CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC. Characterization using UV-Vis, FTIR, DLS, pXRD, and UPLC-PDA confirmed the successful formation of all nanocomposites. Microscopy analysis showed CuO NPs encapsulated within spherical LNPs and embedded in a net-like structure formed by CNFs. The release of Cu ions measured by TXRF over 15 days showed that CuO-LNPs release Cu ions significantly slower than CuO NPs due to the strong interactions between CuO and LNPs. In contrast, CuO-CNFs NC exhibited similar release rates to CuO NPs, attributed to weaker binding. In vitro testing on tobacco BY-2 cells corroborated with slow release profile. CuO NPs and CuO-CNFs NC, which reduced cell viability after 7 days, CuO-LNPs NC maintained plant cell viability and showed no cytotoxicity. Overall, this integrated approach increases the value of biomass for the production of high-value nanomaterials that promotes environmental and economic sustainability, while envisaging CuO-LNPs NC as a potential slow-release nanomaterial for sustainable agriculture.

1. Introduction

Nanotechnology holds considerable potential for sustainable agriculture to meet the growing demand for food. Due to their small size, nanoparticles (NPs) can break through the exclusion barrier of the plant cell wall and penetrate the plant, facilitating the delivery of agrochemicals. Some NPs can act as nanofertilizers due to their nutrient content, others act as nanopesticides due to their inherent pesticidal properties (e.g. silver, titanium and copper NPs), while some are used as nanocarriers due to their special structural properties that allow strong binding (e.g. biopolymer-based NPs, clay-based NPs and carbon-based NPs) [1–3].

Among the various nanomaterials, Cu-based nanomaterials have attracted great interest in agriculture and are a promising alternative to increase crop yields and control diseases [4]. In nanoform, Cu-based

nanomaterials offer many advantages over other traditional agrochemicals and improve plant growth under extreme conditions [4–6]. CuO NPs, for example, improve the salt tolerance of barley plants and the antifungal activity against the plant pathogen *Fusarium oxysporum* [7,8]. Although CuO NPs have many benefits in agriculture, many studies have also found that CuO NPs at higher concentrations show phytotoxicity in plants and crops such as mung bean (*Vigna radiata* L.) [9], soybean (*Glycine max* cv. Kowsar) [10], wheat [11] and rice grains [12]. CuO NPs also affected microorganisms such as rhizobacteria, *Bacillus megaterium* [13] and the soil invertebrate *Enchytraeus crypticus* [14]. Therefore, the toxicity of CuO NPs cannot be ignored as their prolonged use leads to accumulation in the soil and poses a risk to the entire ecosystem. Therefore, controlled and sustained release of Cu ions from CuO NPs in soil is crucial to reduce toxicity while maintaining benefits. This emphasises the need for safer, sustainable agricultural techniques that can

* Corresponding authors at: Institute' of Plant Genetics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Strzeszyńska 34, 60-479 Poznan, Poland.

E-mail addresses: fgre@igr.poznan.pl (G. Franklin), m.dibyendu@jainuniversity.ac.in, dmon@igr.poznan.pl (D. Mondal).

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reduce the toxicity of CuO NPs without compromising the benefits. This problem can be solved by entrapping/functionalising CuO NPs with suitable polymers that can slow down their ion release.

An ideal host for entrapment of CuO NPs should be biodegradable, inexpensive and non-toxic. In this direction, researchers are focussing on green and renewable biodegradable polymers such as chitosan, lignin, cellulose, etc. [15]. These naturally occurring biopolymers have many advantages: they are renewable, biodegradable, biocompatible and cost-effective. Therefore, functionalisation of CuO NPs with biopolymers is desirable [16]. It was observed that the nanocomposite (NC) of CuO coated with a biopolymer (chitosan) acted as both a nanofertilizer and a nanopesticide [17]. Similarly, CuO NPs in a hydrogel of chitosan and acrylic acid improved the nutrient uptake of lettuce infected with *Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lactucae* [18]. The incorporation of biopolymers with CuO NPs is therefore advantageous. Although chitosan has several advantages, it suffers from the limitations of low mechanical strength and dissolves easily in an acidic medium, while lignin and cellulose, on the other hand, have better mechanical properties and stability [19]. Various combinations of CuO NPs with lignin or cellulose have been reported using different synthesis methods, such as lignin-mediated in situ synthesis of CuO NPs on cellulose nanofibers, lignin-assisted solid-phase synthesis of CuO NPs, and lignin-capped CuO NCs [20–22]. However, bionanocomposites combining lignin nanoparticles (LNPs) with CuO NPs, and cellulose nanofibers (CNFs) with CuO NPs, remain largely unexplored.

The plant biomass that remains after the extraction of phytochemicals is often disposed of as waste. However, this lignocellulosic biomass is a rich source of valuable biopolymers such as lignin, cellulose and hemicellulose [23]. The extraction and utilisation of these biopolymers therefore not only improves the environmental sustainability and cost efficiency of the entire process, but is also in line with the principles of a circular economy [24]. Biopolymers such as lignin and cellulose are derived from lignocellulosic biomass, an abundant renewable resource. Cellulose consists of repeating glucose molecules connected by β -1,4-glycosidic bonds. Each unit has three hydroxyl functional groups that help its modifications and bonds with other molecules. Cellulose in nanoform improves the efficiency of nutrient delivery and water uptake capacity of the plant [15]. Similarly, lignin is an aromatic biopolymer consisting of *p*-hydroxyphenyl (H), guaiacyl (G) and syringyl (S) units. It contains several active functional groups such as aliphatic hydroxyl, phenolic hydroxyl and carbonyl groups as well as an unshared electron pair on the oxygen atom, all of which are helpful in metal ion chelation [25]. Various lignin-based metal chelates containing K, Fe, Zn, Mn etc. have been reported as fertilizers [26,27]. At the nanoscale, certain properties of lignin, such as antibacterial and antioxidant properties, are further enhanced due to the higher number of surface phenolic moieties and thermal stability [25]. Furthermore, due to their small size and negative zeta potential, LNPs can improve the uptake and translocation of substances in plants. LNPs could therefore release fertilizers and pesticides in a slow and controlled manner. As described above, we hypothesize that the combination of CNFs and LNPs with CuO NPs can reduce the dissolution of Cu ions, potentially mitigating CuO-induced nanotoxicity in plants and the environment. Furthermore, we propose that the production of these CuO-based bionanocomposites from lignocellulosic biomass could contribute to the circular economy and sustainable development via a biorefinery approach.

The present study demonstrates a circular biomass valorisation approach to synthesize CuO-based bionanocomposites functionalized with LNPs and CNFs, respectively, using *Hypericum perforatum* L. lignocellulosic biomass enriched with phytochemicals. First, a green synthesis of CuO NPs was performed using *H. perforatum* extract, while lignin and cellulose were extracted from the remaining biomass. These biopolymers were further converted into LNPs and CNFs and then functionalized with CuO NPs to form CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC. The CuO-based bionanocomposites were characterized by various analytical methods and the effect of the LNPs and CNFs on the release of

Cu ions from the CuO NPs was investigated by the dialysis method. Furthermore, the Cu ions release profile was validated by evaluating the viability of plant cells and the growth of tobacco BY-2 cells under *in vitro* conditions. Overall, the comprehensive approach realising the full potential of a lignocellulosic biomass for the production of advanced functional nanomaterials promotes environmental sustainability and improves economic viability while targeting CuO-based bionanocomposites as promising candidates for sustainable agricultural applications.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

H. perforatum plants were gathered from the campus of the Institute of Plant Genetics, Polish Academy of Sciences in Poznań, Poland. CuSO₄·5H₂O, sodium hydroxide (NaOH), hydrochloric acid (HCl), nitric acid (HNO₃), ethanol and methanol were purchased from Merck, Sigma Aldrich, Germany. All solvents were of analytical grade (Sigma Aldrich, Germany). Merck Milli-Q ultrapure water was used in the experiments.

2.1.1. Preparation of plant extract

The harvested plant material was first finely ground with a mortar and pestle and then freeze-dried at -50°C under a vacuum pressure of 0.015 mbar in a lyophilizer (Heto-Holten, Denmark). The plant extract of *H. perforatum* was prepared as previously described [28]. In brief, 2 g of dried *H. perforatum* was added to 20 mL of an 80 % aqueous methanol solution (v/v) and sonicated for 10 minutes (min) in an ultrasonicator (Sonorex, Bandelin, Berlin, Germany). The mixture was then stirred for 1 h at a speed of 150 rpm on an orbital shaker (Orbi-Shaker XL, Benchmark Scientific, NJ, USA). It was then centrifuged at 15,000 xg for 30 min (J2-21M/E, JA-20 rotor, Beckman, UK). The supernatant was collected and the methanol was evaporated under vacuum at 35°C using a rotary evaporator (BuchiR114). The resulting mixture was added to Milli-Q water to obtain 100 mL of aqueous extract. This aqueous plant extract was used for the preparation of CuO NPs.

2.1.2. Extraction of lignin and cellulose from biomass

The dried residual biomass obtained after the preparation of the methanolic extract was used for the extraction of lignin and cellulose according to a previously described method with some modifications [29,30]. First, 1 g of the dried biomass was suspended in 100 mL of a 4 % NaOH solution and heated at 80°C for 4 h. The solution was then filtered and the obtained solid residue containing cellulose was separated from the black liquor containing lignin and hemicellulose. The extraction of lignin from the black liquor was carried out according to the previously described method [29]. First, 5 N HCl solution was added to the black liquor to achieve a pH value of 2, as lignin is insoluble in acid and is therefore precipitated. The subsequent precipitates were centrifuged at 10,733 xg (Allegra 21R, F0850 rotor, Beckman Coulter, US) for 10 min and then cleaned with distilled water to remove acid and salt and freeze-dried overnight at -56°C . The resulting lignin precipitates were 200 mg g⁻¹ biomass. The extraction of cellulose from the residual biomass obtained after lignin removal was based on the literature [30]. First, the residual biomass was washed several times with water. The product was then bleached and acidified with a mixture of sodium chlorite and glacial acetic acid to remove all residual lignin and hemicellulose and obtain a holocellulosic pulp. The pulp was then washed with KOH solution, followed by acetic acid and ethanol to obtain cellulose.

2.1.3. Synthesis of lignin NPs (LNPs)

The ethanol nanoprecipitation method described by Figueiredo et al. [31] was used for the synthesis of LNPs. Briefly, lignin extracted from *H. perforatum* biomass was added in 70 % aqueous ethanol solution [v/v] at an initial concentration of 10 mg mL⁻¹ and the obtained solution was stirred overnight. Subsequently, 50 mL of the solution was filtered

through a 0.45 μm syringe filter to remove all undissolved impurities. Then 190 mL of Milli-Q water was quickly added and stirred overnight. After stirring overnight, the resulting LNPs were collected by centrifugation at 10,733 $\times g$ for 30 min and washed with Milli-Q water. The LNPs were resuspended in water again, sonicated for 1 h and then freeze-dried.

2.1.4. Synthesis of cellulose NFs (CNFs)

The CNFs were obtained by acid hydrolysis according to the method of Kian et al. [32], with the exception that 62 wt% sulphuric acid was replaced by 99 % acetic acid. Hydrolysis was carried out at a ratio of 1:20 (g mL^{-1}) cellulose to acetic acid and homogenised under magnetic stirring and at 75–80 °C for 120 min. In the next step, the reaction was quenched by dilution with 20-fold excess water at 4 °C to partially neutralise the pH. The hydrolysed fibre was then centrifuged at 6654 $\times g$ (Allegra 21R, C1015 rotor, Beckman Coulter, US) and washed 7–8 times with deionised water to maintain a pH of 6. The suspension was then dialysed using special dialysis membranes (Sigma-Aldrich, average flat width 10 mm, ref. D9277-100FT). Subsequently, the nanocellulose was obtained by freeze-drying the dialysed solution.

2.1.5. Green synthesis of copper oxide NPs

The green synthesis of CuO NPs followed a previously described method with some modifications [33]. In brief, 5 mL of the prepared 2 % aqueous *H. perforatum* extract was added to 45 mL of a 5 mM $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution. The pH of the solution was maintained at 10.5 using 1 N NaOH. The solution was stirred at 400 rpm on a magnetic stirrer and heated at 80 °C for 5 h. The resulting NPs were centrifuged at 10,733 $\times g$ for 10 min and washed 3-times with deionised water. The resulting CuO NPs were dried for 48 h at 60 °C.

2.1.6. Synthesis of CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC

To synthesize CuO-LNPs NC, the CuO NPs and LNPs were mixed in a ratio of 1: 3 (w/w). First, 50 mg CuO NPs were added to 50 mL ultrapure water in a 100 mL beaker and sonicated for 30 min to obtain a completely homogenised suspension. In another beaker, 150 mg LNPs were suspended in 150 mL ultrapure water and sonicated for 30 min. The resulting solutions were mixed and sonicated again for 1 h and then stirred at 400 rpm for 3 h. The resulting precipitates were centrifuged at 10,733 $\times g$ for 10 min and then freeze-dried at –56 °C. A similar procedure was used for the synthesis of CuO-CNFs NC from CuO NPs and CNFs.

2.2. Characterization

The formation of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC were confirmed using a UV–vis spectrophotometer (UV-1800, Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) in the wavelength range from 200 nm to 800 nm with a resolution of 1 nm. The particle size and zeta potential of the NPs and NCs were determined using the dynamic light scattering spectrometer (DLS) Litesizer DLS 500 (Anton Paar, Austria). The surface morphology of the NPs and NCs were determined by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) using a JEOL JSM-7100F scanning electron microscope, and their size and shape were analysed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a Hitachi HT7700 with EDX. The average size of NPs and NCs were determined from TEM images analysed using ImageJ software. Particle size distributions were plotted using OriginPro 8.5 software. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy was performed to determine different functional groups in the NPs and NCs. It was recorded using an FT-IR spectrometer (IFS 66v/S Bruker) in transmission mode in the range of 400 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . The crystallinity of the NPs and NCs was determined using a powder X-ray diffractometer (pXRD) on a RIGAKU instrument operating with Cu K α 1 radiation, a wavelength (λ) = 0.154 nm) at a scan rate of 3° min^{-1} and a 2-theta range of 5–80°. The phytochemicals present in the CuO NPs were analysed by ultra-performance

liquid chromatography with photodiode array (UPLC-PDA) (Acquity, Waters) [28]. To perform UPLC-PDA, the green synthesized CuO NPs were washed with 80 % methanol and the resulting solution was analysed to find out which compounds acted as capping agents.

2.3. Long term Cu ion release kinetics from CuO NPs, CuO-LNPs NC, and CuO-CNFs NC

The release of Cu ions from CuO NPs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC was performed by dialysis experiment using similar protocols as in our previous report [34,35]. In this experiment, 100 ppm solutions of CuO NPs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC were prepared in ultrapure water and sonicated for 30 min. The pH value of CuO NPs dispersed in ultrapure water was 6.63, for CuO-CNF NCs 6.35 and for CuO-LNPs NCs 5.38. All experiments were carried out at room temperature (20 ± 2 °C). The sonicated samples (1 mL) were then placed in 2 mL polypropylene beakers with an integrated low binding dialysis membrane (MINI Dialysis Devices, 20 kDa MWCO, Slide-A-Lyzer®, ThermoScientific, USA). The dialysis vials with the samples were placed in 50 mL tubes filled with 44.5 mL ultrapure water. The tubes were kept on an orbital shaker with a stirring speed of 120 rpm. The dialysis experiment was continued for 15 days. At different time intervals (0 h, 1 h, 3 h, 6 h, 24 h to 15 days), 1 mL of solution was withdrawn from each tube from the surrounding medium to assess the release of copper ion, and 1 mL of fresh ultrapure water was added as a replacement to maintain the volume. The collected samples were analysed using the total reflectance X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (TXRF) “S2 picofox” (BrukerNano, GmbH, Germany) to quantify the copper ion release. For the quantification of the metal in the TXRF, an internal standard is usually added, which should not already be present in the sample. Here, gallium was used as an internal standard [36]. In brief, 100 μL of the collected sample was spiked with a fixed concentration of gallium and mixed well with a vortex. Then, 10 μL of the sample was placed on a siliconised quartz disc and dried at 60–70 °C for 15–20 min. The discs were carefully placed on a cassette and analysed in the TXRF spectrometer.

2.4. In-vitro plant cell viability and growth study

To investigate the effect of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC on living cells, an *in vitro* study was performed using tobacco BY-2 cells (RIKEN BRC, Kyoto, Japan). The cells were maintained in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 70 mL Murashige and Skoog (MS) liquid medium (Duchefa Biochemie, Haarlem, The Netherlands) supplemented with 1 mg L^{-1} 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid. Cultures were grown on an orbital shaker (Benchmark Scientific, USA) at 110 rpm in a culture room with a 16/8 h light/dark photoperiod, irradiance of 80 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 70 % relative humidity and temperature of 25 °C. A one-week-old suspension culture was subcultured into fresh medium (20 mL) and the cell concentration was adjusted to 20 mg mL^{-1} . After a 24 h incubation in the growth chamber, CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC were added at the following concentrations: 2.5 mg L^{-1} CuO NPs, 7.5 mg L^{-1} LNPs, 7.5 mg L^{-1} CNFs, and CuO-LNPs NC (10 mg L^{-1}) and CuO-CNFs NC (10 mg L^{-1}) at a ratio of 1:3 (w/w). The effects of these treatments on cell growth and viability were observed over a period of seven days. To determine biomass, 1 mL of the culture was collected after seven days, transferred to a 1.5 mL centrifuge tube, centrifuged and the supernatant discarded. The pellet was then weighed. The viability of the cells in the control and treated cultures was determined using the trypan blue exclusion assay. In brief, 100 μL of the cell suspension was mixed with an equal volume of a 0.4 % trypan blue solution (T8154, Sigma-Aldrich, Poznań, Poland). After 2 min, 10 μL of the mixture was spread on a glass slide and imaged using a microscope (Axio Imager, Zeiss). The total number of cells was counted and cell viability was calculated as a percentage of unstained cells. All experiments were performed in triplicate. To quantify intracellular reactive oxygen species (ROS), 1.0 mL of culture from the control and all

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of *H. perforatum* plant extract mediated green synthesis of CuO NPs, extraction of lignin and cellulose and formation of CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. (a) UV-vis spectra, (b) particles size distribution, (c) zeta potential, and (d) powder XRD spectra of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC.

Fig. 3. (a) UPLC-PDA analysis of phytochemicals used as capping agent for CuO NPs and (b) FTIR spectra of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC.

treatments were transferred to separate Eppendorf tubes at different time intervals. Then, 10 μ M H₂DCFDA (C6827, Thermo-Fischer Scientific) was added to each tube, followed by vortexing and incubation in the dark for 15 min. Centrifugation was then performed. For the measurement of ROS, 50 μ L of the supernatant was mixed with 250 μ L of sterile distilled water and the fluorescence of the resulting mixture was measured using a Synergy™ HTX Multi-Mode Microplate Reader (Bio-Tek, USA) with an excitation wavelength of 485 nm and an emission wavelength of 528 nm.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Each treatment was performed in triplicate, and all experiments were repeated independently at least three times. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA, followed by Dunnett's Multiple Comparison Test in GraphPad Prism version 10 for Windows (California, USA).

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Circular valorisation of *H. perforatum* biomass to CuO-based bionanocomposites and their characterisations

The overall scheme of the extraction of biomolecules and biopolymers from the biomass of *H. perforatum* and their subsequent utilisation in the fabrication of CuO-based bionanocomposites is shown in Fig. 1. *H. perforatum* served a dual purpose: its phytochemicals extracted in methanol were used for the synthesis of CuO NPs and the residual biomass was utilised for the extraction of two major biopolymers, lignin and cellulose. These extracted biopolymers were further converted into CNFs and LNPs and then functionalized with CuO NPs to produce the CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC. This is the first report showing the complete utilisation of *H. perforatum* - the use of its phytochemicals for nanoparticle synthesis and its residual biomass for further value addition in functional bionanocomposites. This approach addresses a major

shortcoming in green synthesis, where plant residues are often discarded. By converting waste into functional components, the method improves both environmental sustainability and economic viability. The nanomaterials synthesized in this way were characterized using UV–vis spectroscopy, FTIR, DLS, SEM-EDX, pXRD, UPLC-PDA.

3.1.1. UV–Vis analysis

Fig. 2a shows clear absorption peaks for each material, with the CuO NPs showing a distinct peak at 274 nm, which confirms the formation of CuO NPs and is also consistent with the literature [37]. The lignin showed a peak at 280 nm, confirming the formation of lignin, while the LNPs showed a characteristic peak at 276 nm, which is also consistent with the literature, as aromatic structures and carbonyl groups in lignin absorb in the UV region at 250–400 nm [29]. CNFs showed a distinct peak at 282 nm, which is also consistent with the literature [38]. The formation of CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC was confirmed as CuO-LNPs NC showed two distinct peaks at 282 nm (shifted) and 428 nm (new peak), while CuO-CNFs NC showed a characteristic peak at 284 nm. All these distinct peaks confirm the formation of these nanomaterials, which were further analysed with DLS and zeta potential.

3.1.2. Particles size analysis

The particle size and zeta potential of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC are shown in Fig. 2b&c and their details are given in Table S1, Supporting Information. The average particle size of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC are 127.6 ± 1.48 nm, 89.7 ± 3.91 nm, 292 ± 10.5 nm, 212.8 ± 3.47 nm and 206.9 ± 8.9 nm, respectively. The increasing size of the mixtures of CuO NPs and the polymers indicates the formation of nanocomposites. The polydispersity index obtained was 19.7 ± 3.3 %, 16.1 ± 2.6 %, 26.6 ± 2.3 %, 21.0 ± 4.4 % and 19.7 ± 3.3 % for CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC, respectively, indicating a monodisperse nature of the nanomaterials. The zeta potential of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC were -11.6 ± 0.1 mV, -20.1 ± 0.9 mV, -20.1 ± 0.2 mV, -30.2 ± 0.4 mV and -19.2 ± 0.6 mV, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2c. The negative zeta potential shows the stability of the NPs in solution, as it indicates the repulsion between the particles that prevents them from coagulating. Similar observations have been made in the literature [39,40].

3.1.3. Powder X-ray diffraction spectra (pXRD)

The crystallinity of the green synthesized nanomaterials was determined by a pXRD study and is shown in Fig. 2d. The obtained results show that different diffraction peaks at 2θ values 29.53° , 36.64° , 38.22° , 53.14° and 58.32° correspond to CuO NPs. The specific peaks at ~ 20 , 38.22° , 53.14° and 58.32° correspond to the (111), (020) and (202) crystalline planes, respectively, confirming the monoclinic structure of CuO NPs. The results obtained are also in agreement with a previous study [41]. The pXRD pattern of the LNPs showed characteristic peaks, 2θ at 21.64° , 32.55° and 42.20° . The peak at 21.64° indicates that the LNPs have a lower degree of crystallization and the values obtained are in good agreement with the pXRD patterns of nano-lignin published in the literature [42]. The obtained XRD pattern of CNFs showed a high intensity of peaks at a 2θ value of 22.36° , representing the crystalline planes (200), and some small peaks at 2θ values of 34.66° , 40.6° and 45.64° , showing the crystalline structure of CNFs. Similar results have been reported in the literature [39,43]. The XRD pattern of CuO-LNPs NC showed sharp peaks at 2θ values of 23.06° and 41.96° , indicating an interaction between CuO NPs and LNPs. Similarly, the obtained peaks of CuO-CNFs NC showed the values of 22.42° , 29.6° , 35.08° and 40.38° , which represent a combination of CuO NPs and CNFs mixture. The peak at 22.42° , which corresponds to the crystalline plane (200), represents the presence of cellulose NFs and the presence of peaks at 29.6° and 35.08° corresponds to the (110) and (111) planes of CuO in the CuO-CNFs NC, respectively.

3.1.4. UPLC-PDA and FTIR

In our previous study, we found that among the various phytochemicals present in the methanolic extract of *H. perforatum*, phenolic acids and flavonoids act as reducing agents for metal ions, whereas xanthenes and phloroglucinols act as capping agents for Ag NPs [28]. Accordingly, the present study attempted to understand which capping agent is involved in the stabilization of CuO NPs using UPLC-PDA. Fig. 3a shows the UPLC-PDA chromatogram of the solution obtained after washing the CuO NPs with 80 % methanol. As can be seen from the UPLC-PDA chromatogram, compounds such as quercetin-3-glycoside, avicularin, 1,3,7-trihydroxyxanthone, 3,3-hydroperoxyfurohyperforin, furohyperforin and adhyperforin were present in the green synthesized CuO NPs and thus these phytochemicals contribute to the CuO NPs as capping agents. This observation is consistent with the FTIR data obtained for CuO NPs (Fig. 3b). In the FTIR spectrum of CuO NPs, the

Fig. 4. FESEM images of (a) CuO NPs, (b) LNPs, (c) CNFs, (d) CuO-LNPs NC, and (e) CuO-CNFs NC. (f) EDX mapping with element overlay of CuO-LNPs NC. The inset shows % of element distribution.

Fig. 5. TEM images of CuO NPs (a), LNPs (c), CNFs (e), CuO-LNPs NC (g), and CuO-CNf NC (i). Size distribution calculated from TEM images of CuO NPs (b), LNPs (d), CNFs (f), CuO-LNPs NC (h).

characteristic peaks at 3400 cm^{-1} , 2925 cm^{-1} , 1613 cm^{-1} , 1580 cm^{-1} , 1492 cm^{-1} and 1092 cm^{-1} represent O—H stretching, C—H stretching, C=O stretching, C=C stretching and -C-O stretching, respectively. All these functionalities are present in the capping agents shown in Fig. 3a. The characteristic peaks at 472 cm^{-1} represent Cu—O stretching vibrations and confirm the formation of CuO NPs [40].

The FTIR spectra of LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNf NC are shown in Fig. 3b. In the FTIR spectrum of LNPs, the specific peak at 3301 cm^{-1} represents the O—H stretching vibrations of the phenolic or aliphatic -OH groups, the peaks at 2924 cm^{-1} and 2851 cm^{-1} show the C—H stretching in the -CH₃ and -CH₂ groups, the peaks at 1384 cm^{-1} and 1127 cm^{-1} show the presence of the syringyl moiety and the peaks at 1536 cm^{-1} and 1241 cm^{-1} show the presence of the guaiacyl moiety of lignin. The peaks at 1653 cm^{-1} and 1455 cm^{-1} represent the aromatic ring stretching of the *p*-hydroxyphenyl moiety in lignin [44]. The FTIR spectra of the CNFs show the functional groups present in the cellulose nanofibers. The main functional groups of cellulose were identified at 896 cm^{-1} (β -glycosidic bond), 1061 cm^{-1} (C-O-C stretching vibration of the pyranose ring), $2852\text{--}2917\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C—H stretching of the CH₂ group) and 3398 cm^{-1} (free O—H stretching of cellulose). The peaks at 1373 cm^{-1} , 1160 cm^{-1} represent the asymmetric C—H deformation enhanced by the high purity cellulose nanofibers. The results obtained are in agreement with those published in the literature [32,39]. In the FTIR spectrum of CuO LNPs, NC showed a shifted peaks at 3407 cm^{-1} , which represents the H-bonding between the phytochemicals of CuO NPs and the functional groups of LNPs. A strongly shifted peak at 1620 cm^{-1} represents the C=C stretching vibration, confirming the $\diamond - \diamond$ interaction between the phytochemicals around the CuO NPs and the functional groups of the LNPs. The appearance of a new peak at 1414 cm^{-1} and the weakening of the peaks at 1455 cm^{-1} and 1384 cm^{-1} of CuO shows the strong interactions between CuO NPs and LNPs. Moreover, the new

peaks at 1116 cm^{-1} and 622 cm^{-1} confirm their interaction. In the CuO-CNf NC, the shifted peaks at 3445 cm^{-1} show the H-bonding between CNFs and CuO NPs, the disappearance of the peak at 2852 cm^{-1} and the appearance of a single sharp peak at 2912 cm^{-1} show the interaction between CuO NPs and CNFs. A similarly shifted peak at 1630 cm^{-1} represents the non-covalent bonding between CuO NPs and CNFs. The remaining peaks show the presence of both CNFs and CuO NPs. Overall, the FTIR, UV-vis, DLS, zeta potential and pXRD results demonstrated successful fabrication of CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNf NC from green synthesized CuO NPs.

3.1.5. Surface morphology

Following the successful eco-engineering of CuO-based nanocomposites from LNPs and CNFs, we have investigated the surface morphology and shape of such NCs using FESEM. Fig. 4a-e show the FESEM images of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNf NC. Fig. 4a represents the spherical and hemispherical shape of CuO NPs, which is typical of green synthesized CuO NPs as described in the literature [45]. The LNPs are a spherical shape as shown in Fig. 4b, which is also consistent with the literature [42]. The CNFs show a filamentous network structure, as shown in Fig. 4c [46]. Fig. 4d represents presence of CuO NPs and LNPs in the CuO-LNPs NC, which confirms that the CuO NPs are surrounded by LNPs. Due to the polar surface of spherical lignin NPs, they provide a better adsorption surface for metal NPs [47]. Additionally, the aromatic structure of lignin together with its functional groups enhances its chelating ability to bind metal oxide NPs. Fig. 4e also shows a spherical and filamentary structure in which the CuO NPs are surrounded by CNFs, confirming the formation of the CuO-CNf NC. The elemental distribution of copper, carbon and oxygen in the CuO-LNPs NC was analysed by energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping and the image with the elemental overlay is shown in Fig. 4f.

Fig. 6. (a) Slow-release profile of Cu ions from CuO NPs, CuO/Lignin NC, CuO/cellulose NC. All values shown are the mean \pm SEM of three replicates ($n = 3$). Mean values are significantly different at $P < 0.001$ (***) compared to control (one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test). (b) interaction mechanism of CuO NPs with lignin NPs and (c) interaction mechanism of CuO NPs with cellulose NFs.

The results show that carbon and oxygen are predominantly distributed around the copper, indicating successful conjugation of the LNPs with CuO NPs. EDX analysis (Fig. 4f) further confirms this and shows that the NCs contains about 40 % carbon, 53 % oxygen and 7 % copper — indicating a high presence of the LNPs around the CuO NPs. The copper content in CuO-LNPs NC analysed by TXRF (7.97 %) agrees well with the value determined by SEM-EDX mapping. The SEM-EDX mapping image of CuO-CNFs NC with element overlay is shown in Fig. S1 (Supporting Information), where the distribution of copper within the CNFs network is clearly visible. The presence of carbon (30 %), oxygen (57 %) and copper (12 %) also confirms that CuO is distributed within the CNFs in CuO-CNFs NC. The value of copper in CuO-CNFs NC is almost identical to the value determined by TXRF (9.67 %).

After examining the surface morphology of the different NCs by FESEM, we performed a TEM analysis to gain further insight into the morphology and size of the different NCs. Fig. 5a-i shows TEM images and the size distribution of CuO NPs, LNPs, CNFs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC. As shown in Fig. 5a&b, the CuO NPs have both spherical and hemispherical shapes with an average size of 4.16 ± 1.2 nm. The LNPs are also almost spherical with an average size of 14.4 ± 2.6 nm (Fig. 5c&d). The CNFs showed a web-like structure of nanofibers with an average diameter of 28.1 ± 10.3 nm (Fig. 5e&f). The formation of CuO-LNPs NC can be clearly seen in Fig. 5g&h, where CuO NPs are embedded in LNPs with an average size of 6.1 ± 1.6 nm. Similarly, the formation of CuO-CNFs NC was also confirmed by an image of CuO NPs within CNFs as shown in Fig. 5i. A similar image of CuO-CNFs NC was also obtained in the FESEM study (Fig. 4e). Thus, the TEM images confirm that the formation of CuO NPs and the fabrication of CuO-based NCs occur at the

nanoscale of LNPs and CNFs. Fig. S2 shows the elements present in the synthesized NPs and NCs. In the CuO NPs, the presence of carbon (22.5 %), oxygen (61.8 %) and copper (15.7 %) shows that the CuO NPs are well surrounded by phytochemicals (Fig. S2a). The presence of carbon (27.3 %) and oxygen (72.7 %) was detected in the LNPs (Fig. S2b). The presence of carbon (21.3 %) and oxygen (78.7 %) was also observed in CNFs (Fig. S2c). In the NCs, in addition to carbon and oxygen, the presence of 7.1 % and 9.6 % copper in CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC, respectively, was confirmed by TEM EDX analysis (Fig. S2d&e). Overall, the presence of copper together with carbon and oxygen in the CuO NPs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC confirms the formation of NPs and NCs.

3.2. Study of Cu ion release from green synthesized CuO NPs, CuO-LNPs NC, and CuO-CNFs NC

CuO-based NPs have proven to be effective in combating plant diseases and increasing agricultural productivity. Despite these benefits, such nanofertilizers are applied in large quantities, and their low uptake efficiency can lead to continuous buildup, resulting in nanotoxicity in the environment. Therefore, improving the efficiency of nano-fertilizer use is crucial for promoting sustainable agriculture. Here, the effect of LNPs and CNFs on the release of Cu ions from green synthesized CuO NPs was investigated by dialysis experiment and analysed by TXRF (Table S2, Supporting Information).

Fig. 6a shows the release of Cu ions from CuO NPs, CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC. CuO NPs and its NCs showed a rapid release of Cu ions up to 48 h (Fig. 6a and Table S2) and thereafter the release is almost constant up to 15 days. It was also observed that the release pattern of Cu

Fig. 7. Effect of NPs and nanocomposites [CuO NPs (2.5 mg L^{-1}), LNPs (7.5 mg L^{-1}), CNFs (7.5 mg L^{-1}), CuO-LNPs NC (10 mg L^{-1}), CuO-CNFs NC (10 mg L^{-1})] on BY-2 cells after 7 days of treatment. (a) Photomicrographs of tobacco BY-2 cells stained with trypan blue to assess cell viability. (b) Percentage of viable BY-2 cells after treatment. (c) Fresh weight of BY-2 cells measured 7 days after treatment. All values shown are the mean \pm SEM of three replicates ($n = 3$). Mean values are significantly different at $P < 0.001$ (*) compared to control (one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

ions from CuO-LNPs NC was different from that of CuO NPs and CuO-CNFs NC. The CuO-LNPs NC showed a release of 1/3 of Cu ions compared to the control CuO NPs, while the CuO-CNFs NC showed an almost similar release rate to the CuO NPs. The reason for this can be explained with the help of possible interactions between CuO NPs with LNPs and CNFs, as shown in Fig. 6b&c. The plausible mechanism of interaction between green-synthesized CuO NPs and LNPs is mainly attributed to H-bonding and π - π interactions. Lignin contains various hydroxyl and phenolic functional groups as well as an aromatic structure that contributes to π -bonds. Moreover, the CuO NPs are capped with phytochemicals containing similar functional groups, which favours these interactions. In addition, lignin is reported to be an excellent biopolymer for chelation of metals and metal oxides, which enables a strong interaction between LNPs and CuO NPs [26,27]. The aromatic structure coupled with multiple interaction sites improved the encapsulation properties of the LNPs for CuO NPs and this could be a reason for the slow release of Cu ions from CuO-LNPs NC. In the case of CuO-CNFs NC, the binding of CuO NPs with the CNFs is limited to the H-bond, which is somewhat less effective, and therefore the release of Cu ions from CuO-CNFs NC is almost the same as that of green synthesized CuO NPs.

3.3. Effect of green synthesized CuO NPs, CuO-LNPs NC, and CuO-CNFs NC on cell viability and growth of tobacco BY-2 cells

The observed slow release of Cu ions, in particular the significantly sustained release of CuO-LNPs NC compared to CuO NPs and CuO-CNFs NC (Fig. 6a), suggests that such controlled release could help to reduce Cu-induced toxicity in plant systems. To test this, the cytotoxic effects and biocompatibility of the CuO-based bionanocomposites were investigated using tobacco BY-2 cells. The *in vitro* studies on plant cells showed that a higher concentration (50 mg L^{-1}) of CuO NPs significantly reduced cell viability compared to a lower concentration (2.5 mg L^{-1}). A similar trend was observed for LNPs, whereas CNFs did not affect cell viability, even at the highest concentration tested (150 mg L^{-1}) (Supplementary Table S3). To assess the effect of slow release, nanocomposites containing 2.5 mg L^{-1} CuO NPs and 7.5 mg L^{-1} LNPs or CNFs were selected. As shown in Fig. 7a&b, even at a concentration of 2.5 mg L^{-1} CuO NPs, a significantly lower viability of plant cells was observed compared to the control. In contrast, 7.5 mg L^{-1} LNPs had no effect on cell viability. Interestingly, when CuO NPs were incorporated into LNPs to form CuO-LNPs NCs, a significant improvement in the viability of BY-2 cells (Fig. 7a&b) was observed compared to CuO NPs. We also observed that CuO NPs and CuO-CNFs NCs elicited higher ROS production than the control and other treatments, suggesting that oxidative stress contributed to the observed cell toxicity in these treatments (Fig. S3). Although CuO-LNPs NCs initially showed a slight, non-significant increase in ROS levels, the fluorescence remained comparable to the control over time, providing further evidence that the controlled release of Cu ions from the nanocomposite effectively limits oxidative stress. Although the BY-2 cells treated with CNFs exhibited similar cell viability to the control cells, functionalization of CNFs with CuO NPs resulted in significantly lower cell viability compared to the control group. This could be attributed to the weak interaction between CNFs and CuO NPs, which resulted in a similar release of Cu ions as observed with the CuO NPs alone. (Fig. 6a&c). The biomass obtained after 7 days reflected the same trend of cell viability after treatment with the different nanomaterials (Fig. 7c). These results suggest that the use of CuO-LNPs NC is a promising route for the safe application of Cu-based nanomaterials in agriculture, as it would help to reduce the harmful effects on plants while maintaining their benefits.

4. Conclusion

In summary, we synthesized various NPs and NCs using *H. perforatum* in a biorefinery approach. The phytochemicals extracted from the

H. perforatum plant were used for the synthesis of CuO NPs and the biomass (which is usually discarded) was used for the extraction of lignin and cellulose. The extracted lignin and cellulose were further converted into LNPs and CNFs, respectively, and then combined with CuO NPs to form CuO-LNPs NC and CuO-CNFs NC. This approach maximizes plant material utility, reduces waste, and supports a green, circular bioeconomy. Green-synthesized CuO NPs and their bionanocomposites were tested for slow Cu ions release using a 15-day dialysis experiment. CuO-LNPs NCs showed a threefold slower Cu ions release than CuO NPs, likely due to strong hydrogen bonding and π - π interactions between LNPs and CuO. CuO-CNFs NC released Cu ions at a rate similar to CuO NPs. *In vitro* tests using tobacco BY-2 plant cells demonstrated that CuO NPs reduced cell viability, while CuO-LNPs NCs improved it, suggesting the diminished toxicity from slower ion release. However, CuO-CNFs NCs decreased viability similarly to CuO NPs, correlating with their comparable ion release rates. The biomass growth rate was consistent with the viability results. This suggests the potential of CuO-LNPs NC in controlled release applications with improved plant cell viability and growth. Overall, the proposed strategy offers a green, cost-effective, and eco-friendly approach by fully utilizing lignocellulosic biomass, minimizing waste, and producing value-added CuO-based bionanocomposites that promote sustainable agriculture. This study encourages further research aimed at applying the current formulations in field trials, evaluating their effects on soil microbes and scaling up the production process.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Megha Saxena: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Lakshmiathy Muthukrishnan:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Matam Pradeep:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Rajendran K. Selvakesavan:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Gregory Franklin:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Dibyendu Mondal:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.146474>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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